

ISic0654

I.Sicily inscription 0654

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Sicilia

Place of origin (modern)

Sicily

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Amsterdam, Netherlands, Amsterdam University Library, inventory 238

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 494115

EDCS 3700327

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1993.0827

Te Riele, G.J.M.J. 1977. Greek texts in the possession of the Amsterdam University Library. Appendix: Les pierres inscrites. *Talanta*. 8-9: 114-118. At

116-118 pl.5

Solin, H. 1993. *Varia Onomastica*: XI. Ein neuer Gentilname: Rhosinius. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik*. 99: 233-234.

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